

Effect of Nasa Liquid Organic Fertilizer (LOF) Concentration and Varieties on Growth and Production of Lettuce Plants (*Lactuca Sativa L.*) with the DFT Hydroponic System

Pamuji Setyo Utomo¹, Muhammad Khoirul Anwar², Nunuk Helilusiatiningsih^{3*}
Universitas Islam Kadiri

Corresponding Author: Nunuk Helilusiatiningsih nunukhelilusi@gmail.com

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Lettuce Plant, Nasa Lof, Varieties

Received : 3 December

Revised : 18 December

Accepted: 20 January

©2024 Utomo, Anwar, Helilusiatiningsih : This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Atribusi 4.0 Internasional](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

ABSTRACT

Effect of Nasa Liquid Organic Fertilizer (LOF) Concentration and Varieties on Growth and Production of Lettuce Plants (*Lactuca sativa L.*) with DFT Hydroponic System. Lettuce (*Lactuca sativa L.*) is a short-lived leaf vegetable that can be grown in both highlands and lowlands. Generally consumed in a raw state so that hygiene is a top priority. Currently the demand for lettuce has not been fulfilled optimally, this is due to constraints in cultivation which causes low quality and yield of lettuce production. Efforts to increase lettuce production can be done by adding organic fertilizers as a source of plant nutrition and selecting the right lettuce varieties. This study aims to determine the interaction between the concentration of Nasa LOF fertilizer and lettuce varieties on the growth and production in hydroponic cultivation with DFT system. This study used a factorial randomized block design with a 2-factor treatment design. The first factor is the concentration of Nasa LOF with 3 levels, namely 4 mL/L; 6 mL/L; 8 mL/L and the second factor is the lettuce variety with 3 levels, namely the new grand rapid variety of lettuce; karina; kriebo le 873 which consisted of 3 groups. The results of this study showed an interaction between the concentration of Nasa LOF and lettuce varieties on the observed variables of plant height (24 DAP and 31 DAP), number of leaves (31 DAP) and wet weight per lettuce plant (31 DAP). The single treatment of Nasa LOF concentration had no significant effect on all variables observed in lettuce. The single treatment of lettuce varieties affected the observed variables of plant height (10 DAP and 17 DAP), number of leaves (24 DAP) and root length (10 DAP, 17 DAP, 24 DAP, and 31 DAP)

INTRODUCTION

Lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* L.) is a type of leaf vegetable plant and is classified as an annual (short-lived) plant. Plants grow short with a height ranging from 20-40 cm or more. Morphologically, lettuce leaves have various shapes, sizes and colors, depending on the variety. Lettuce plants have a tap and fibrous root system. Fibrous roots attach to the stem, growing spread out, in all directions. Lettuce plant flowers are yellow, grow densely in a series. Lettuce plant seeds are flat oval in shape, hairy, somewhat hard, brown, dark, and small in size. Hydroponic planting can develop quickly because it has several advantages. The main advantage is that the success of plants to grow and produce is more guaranteed. Hydroponic system technology can be divided into several types based on how the nutrients are provided. DFT (Deep Flow Technique) is a method of cultivating plants in hydroponics that is quite easy to do. Cultivating plants using hydroponics requires proper nutritional management, because the nutrient solution is a source of nutritional supply for plants to obtain nutrients in hydroponic cultivation. The nutrient source commonly used in hydroponic cultivation so far is AB mix nutrient solution, which if used continuously will have a negative impact on the body, therefore in this research the use of AB mix fertilizer is reduced by adding Nasa LOF to fulfill the required nutrients.

The problems that occur are the erratic rainy season and extreme climate changes that can affect lettuce growth and production. The solution to this problem is to study the hydroponic method for cultivating lettuce plants using organic liquid fertilizer of varying concentrations and types. It is suspected that this experiment will hopefully increase production. The novelty of this research is that no research and articles have been reported internationally or nationally. The benefit is that it provides new insight into how to grow lettuce using the hydroponic method which is beneficial for efficiency and has a high selling value.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* L.) is an annual vegetable that can grow in different seasons. This plant is a short-lived leaf vegetable and can be planted in the highlands or lowlands (Rahmawati, 2018). Lettuce is a leaf vegetable that is commonly consumed raw, so hygiene from pesticide residues and dangerous microorganisms is a top priority. Currently, the demand for lettuce has not been met optimally, so the government needs to import lettuce, based on data from the Central Statistics Agency (2019), in Akbar (2020) in 2019 Indonesia imported 171,000 kilograms of lettuce. This is due to obstacles in cultivation which cause low quality and yields of lettuce production, therefore cultivation techniques are needed that pay attention to quality, quantity and continuity so that the products produced can meet market demand. One of them is the hydroponic cultivation technique (Zahima, 2019).

Nasa LOF is a pure organic material in liquid form from livestock and poultry waste, natural and plant waste, certain types of plants which are processed naturally. Nasa LOF has a multi-purpose function, namely apart from being mainly used for all types of food crops (rice, secondary crops, etc.), horticultural (vegetables, fruit, flowers) and annual crops (cocoa, oil palm) it is also used for livestock/poultry and fish/shrimp. The micro nutrient content in 1 liter of Nasa LOF has a function equivalent to the micro nutrient content of 1 ton of manure (Maulana, 2011). The nutrient content in Nasa LOF liquid organic fertilizer is stated on the packaging label, namely N 4.15%, P₂O₅ 4.45%, K₂O 5.66%, C organic 9.69%, Fe 505.5 ppm, Mn 1931.1%, Cu 1179.8%, Zn 1986.1%, B 806.6% , Co 8.4 ppm, Mo 2.3 ppm.

Efforts to increase production to meet lettuce needs can also be done through selecting the right varieties. Plant varieties must be superior varieties, suit market demand, suit the conditions of the planting site, have high productivity and be resistant to pests and diseases. This research used 3 varieties, namely: the 1st variety, namely New Grand Rapid, this lettuce has a plant height of around 15-19 cm, has a short compact shape, has curly leaves with short cylindrical stems and does not form crowns. This lettuce has a slightly sweet, crunchy taste with a harvest age of between 35-42 days after planting. The second variety is Karina, this lettuce has a plant height of around 15-19 cm, leaves are egg-shaped with yellowish green outer leaves. This lettuce has a slightly sweet taste with a harvest age of around 24-25 days after planting with a planting weight of 250-270 g, and the 3rd variety is Kriebo LE 873, this lettuce has a plant height of around 22-30 cm, leaves are egg-shaped with yellowish green outer leaves. This lettuce has a slightly sweet taste.

Based on the various conditions described above, it is necessary to carry out research on cultivating lettuce plants hydroponically by adding liquid organic fertilizer. It is hoped that this research can contribute to efforts to increase the productivity of lettuce plants and meet market needs, especially lettuce needs in Indonesia. The following are the objectives that researchers want to achieve in this research, namely to: determine the interaction between giving Nasa LOF concentration and lettuce varieties on growth and production in DFT system hydroponic cultivation, knowing the effect of giving Nasa LOF concentration on the growth and production of lettuce plants in DFT system hydroponic cultivation. , to find out the effect of lettuce varieties on growth and production in hydroponic cultivation with the DFT system

METHODOLOGY

Time and Place

This research was carried out from February to March 2021. Located in the Greenhouse, Sumberingin Kulon Village, Ngunut District, Tulungagung Regency. The Sumberingin Kulon Village area is a lowland area with an altitude of ± 85 meters above sea level and an average temperature in the greenhouse of 24-25 degrees Celsius.

Tools and Materials

The tools used in this research include cutters, tweezers, trays, TDS meters, pH meters, netpots, buckets, measuring cups, scales, dropper pipettes, spatulas, rulers, stationery, treatment labels and cameras. The materials used in this research include lettuce seeds of the New Grand Rapid variety, Karina variety, Kriebo LE 873 variety, AB mix nutrition, Nasa LOF, H₃PO₄, KOH and sponge.

Research Methods

This research used a factorial randomized block design (RAK) with a 2-factor treatment design. Factor I is Nasa LOF concentration with 3 levels denoted by (K) and factor II is lettuce variety with 3 levels denoted by (V). The design consists of 3 groups with a total of 27 combinations of treatment plots which are determined as follows:

Factor I:

K1=Nasa LOF Concentration 4 mL/L

K2=Nasa LOF Concentration 6 mL/L

K3=Nasa LOF Concentration 8 mL/L

Factor II:

V1=New Grand Rapid Variety Lettuce

V2=Karina Variety Lettuce

V3=Kriebo LE 873 Variety Lettuce

Research Implementation

The stage of this research is preparing a hydroponic installation made with a Deep Flow Technique (DFT) system. Sowing lettuce seeds is done by spreading them on paper towels, then the germinated seeds are transferred to a sponge medium using tweezers. The next stage is making the AB mix solution by dissolving stock A and stock B each in a bucket with a water volume of 5 liters, stirring until completely dissolved and there is no sediment. Lettuce planting is done when the seedlings are 14 days after sowing. The seeds used are uniform seeds with 4 leaves. The Nasa LOF treatment was carried out at the age of 0 HST as much as 40% and at the age of 7 DAP as much as 60%. Plant maintenance carried out includes adding AB mix nutrients with a concentration of 750 ppm when the amount of nutrient solution in the reservoir decreases, maintaining the pH of the solution and paying attention to plant pests. Hydroponic lettuce is harvested when it meets the harvest criteria or when the plant is 31 HST by removing the plant from the planting hole and separating it from the netpot, then placing it in a basket.

Observation Variables

Observational variables observed in this study included plant height (cm), number of leaves (strands), root length (cm), and wet weight per plant (grams).

Data Analysis

Data obtained from observations on each variable are entered into a table to carry out an F test using the variance method (ANOVA). If an interaction occurs, a comparison test is carried out with DMRT, if no interaction occurs, it is continued with a comparison test between factors using the BNT test

RESULTS

Plant Height

Table 1. Average Height of Lettuce Plants Due to the Interaction Between Nasa LOF Concentration and Lettuce Varieties

Treatment Combination	Average Plant Height (cm)	
	24 DAP	31 DAP
K1V1	14,06 e	22,40 c
K1V2	10,37 ab	20,09 bc
K1V3	11,97 cd	20,97 bc
K2V1	15,25 f	25,75 d
K2V2	9,99 a	16,69 a
K2V3	12,26 cd	15,93 a
K3V1	12,27 cd	22,15 c
K3V2	11,27 bc	20,63 bc
K3V3	12,71 d	19,39 b
DMRT 5%	**	**

Note: 1. DAP = Days After Planting

2. Numbers accompanied by the same letter in the same column and the same treatment show no significant difference in their effect on the DMRT test at the 5% level.

Based on the results of the 5% DMRT test (Table 1), it is known that the combination of K2V1 treatment (LOF Nasa concentration 6 mL/L + new grand rapid lettuce variety) at the age of 24 DAP and 31 DAP was significantly different from the treatments K1V1, K1V2, K1V3, K2V2, K2V3, K3V1, K3V2, and K3V3 on lettuce plant height variables. It can be seen in the table that the K2V1 treatment combination produced the highest average at 24 DAP and 31 DAP age observations. This shows that the Nasa LOF concentration of 6 mL/L is the optimal Nasa LOF concentration to increase the height growth of the new grand rapid variety lettuce plants.

Table 2. Average Height of Lettuce Plants Due to the Influence of Nasa LOF Concentration and Lettuce Varieties

Treatment	Average Plant Height (cm)	
	10 DAP	17 DAP
K1	3,61	7,42
K2	3,86	7,87
K3	3,69	7,48
BNT 5%	0,28	0,55
V1	3,48 a	7,52 a
V2	3,51 a	7,17 a
V3	4,17 b	8,09 b
BNT 5%	0,28	0,55

Note: 1. DAP = Days After Planting

2. Numbers accompanied by the same letter in the same column are not significantly different in the 5% BNT test.

Based on the results of the 5% BNT test (Table 2), it is known that in a single treatment the Nasa LOF concentration had no significant effect on observations at 10 DAP and 17 DAP on lettuce plant height. It can be seen in the table that the K2 treatment produced the highest average at 10 DAP and 17 DAP age observations. At the age of 1 DAP to 10 DAP, the plant height still does not exceed the netpot or hydroponic installation pipe, so that the lettuce plant leaves do not receive maximum sunlight so that the photosynthesis of the lettuce plant is not optimal. This is what causes plant height growth at the age of 10 DAP and 17 DAP to be not significantly different.

Based on the results of the 5% BNT test (Table 2), it is known that the single treatment of the V3 lettuce variety (Kriebo LE 873 variety) at the age of 10 DAP and 17 DAP was significantly different from the V1 and V2 treatments regarding lettuce plant height. It can be seen in table 3 that the V3 treatment produced the highest average at 10 DAP and 17 DAP age observations. Based on the description of plant varieties, each lettuce variety has its own growth characteristics. The kriebo le 873 variety has the potential for plant height to exceed that of the karina variety, supported by a faster harvest time than the new grand rapid variety. This is what causes the height growth of lettuce plants to be better than other varieties.

Table 3. Average Number of Leaves on Lettuce Plants Due to the Interaction Between Nasa LOF Concentration and Lettuce Varieties

Treatment Combination	Average Number of Leaves (pieces)	
	31 DAP	
K1V1	9,73	c
K1V2	8,67	ab
K1V3	10,13	cd
K2V1	11,20	d
K2V2	8,47	a
K2V3	9,80	c
K3V1	10,07	cd
K3V2	9,33	bc
K3V3	9,93	c
DMRT 5%	**	

Note: 1. DAP = Days After Planting

2. Numbers accompanied by the same letter in the same column and the same treatment show no significant difference in their effect on the DMRT test at the 5% level.

Based on the results of the 5% DMRT test (Table 4), it is known that the combination of K2V1 treatment (LOF Nasa concentration 6 mL/L + New Grand Rapid variety lettuce) at 31 DAP was not significantly different from the K1V3 and K3V1 treatments, but was significantly different from the K1V1 treatment, K1V2, K2V2, K2V3, K3V2, and K3V3 on the variable number of lettuce leaves. Can be seen in the table that the K2V1 treatment combination produced the highest average at 31 DAT age observations. This shows that the Nasa LOF concentration of 6 mL/L is the optimal Nasa LOF concentration to increase the growth of the number of leaves of the new grand rapid variety lettuce plants.

Table 4. Average Number of Lettuce Plant Leaves Due to the Influence of Nasa LOF Concentration and Lettuce Varieties

Treatment	Average Number of Leaves (pieces)		
	10 DAP	17 DAP	24 DAP
K1	5,04	7,11	8,07
K2	5,11	7,16	8,20
K3	5,13	7,22	8,02
BNT 5%	0,12	0,32	0,61
V1	5,02	7,02	8,33 b
V2	5,16	7,18	7,62 a
V3	5,11	7,29	8,33 b
BNT 5%	0,12	0,32	0,61

Note: 1. DAP = Days After Planting

2. Numbers accompanied by the same letter in the same column are not significantly different in the 5% BNT test

Based on the results of the 5% BNT test (Table 4), it is known that in a single treatment the Nasa LOF concentration had no significant effect on observations at 10 DAT, 17 DAP and 24 DAP on lettuce plant height. It can be said that the growth in the number of leaves is directly proportional to the growth in plant length. The higher the length of the plant, the greater the number of leaves (Zenita, 2019). This is directly proportional to the results of observations of plant height in this study. Based on the results of observations of plant height at 10 DAP and 17 DAP, the Nasa LOF concentration treatment did not show significantly different results. This shows that the growth in plant height does not significantly affect the number of lettuce plant leaves.

Root Length

Table 5. Average Root Length of Lettuce Plants Due to the Influence of Nasa LOF Concentration and Lettuce Varieties

Treatment	Average Root Length (cm)			
	10 DAP	17 DAP	24 DAP	31 DAP
K1	9,10	12,79	15,47	19,17
K2	10,37	13,07	15,44	20,52
K3	10,15	13,83	16,43	21,63
BNT 5%	0,10	0,16	0,95	2,48
V1	6,96 a	11,97 a	15,21 ab	22,24 b
V2	11,18 b	13,26 b	15,15 a	18,03 a
V3	11,48 b	14,46 c	16,99 b	21,06 b
BNT 5%	1,10	1,16	0,95	2,48

Note: 1. DAP = Days After Planting

2. Numbers accompanied by the same letter in the same column are not significantly different in the 5% BNT test

The results of the analysis of variance showed that there was no interaction between Nasa LOF concentration and lettuce varieties on the root length of lettuce plants when observing the root length of lettuce plants. Based on the results of the 5% BNT test (Table 5), it is known that in a single treatment the Nasa LOF concentration had no significant effect on observations at 10 DAP, 17 DAP, 24 DAP and 31 DAP on the root length of lettuce plants. This is because in the hydroponic cultivation technique the plant roots do not grow significantly in length, because in the hydroponic system the water and nutrients needed for planting are already available in the nutrient solution, where the roots are plant organs whose function is to absorb water and nutrients. In accordance with the opinion of Raihan (2017) who states that in hydroponic plant cultivation, plants obtain nutrients from specially prepared nutrient solutions.

Wet Weight Per Plant

Table 6. Average Wet Weight Per Lettuce Plant Due to the Interaction Between Nasa LOF Concentration and Lettuce Variety

Treatment Combination	Wet Weight per Plant (grams)	
	31 DAP	
K1V1	23,40	b
K1V2	15,20	ab
K1V3	20,00	ab
K2V1	40,13	c
K2V2	11,80	a
K2V3	13,20	a
K3V1	22,93	b
K3V2	15,60	ab
K3V3	18,67	ab
DMRT 5%	**	

Note: 1. DAP = Days After Planting

2. Numbers accompanied by the same letter in the same column and the same treatment show no significant difference in their effect on the DMRT test at the 5% level.

DISCUSSION

According to Tuhuture (2020), the addition of Nasa LOF can increase the nutrient content needed by plants, especially macro nutrients such as N. N is known to be important for the vegetative growth of a plant. According to Patti (2016), this was proven in this research which showed that when observing the height of plants aged 24 DAP and 31 HST (Table 1), there was an interaction with the lettuce variety treatment. This is in accordance with the opinion of Talkah (2007) in Murdianto (2016) who said that providing the right organic fertilizer will stimulate plant growth because the function of organic fertilizer is to increase water storage and absorption capacity and enrich macro and micro nutrients. The Nasa LOF concentration treatment is supported by lettuce variety treatment. By choosing the right lettuce variety, nutrient absorption will be more optimal. The height of a plant can also be influenced by genetic factors of the variety. It can be seen in (Table 1) that the highest average yield was observed at the ages

of 24 DAP and 31 DAP, namely in the treatment of the V1 variety (New Grand Rapid variety). This shows that the new grand rapid variety has good plant height characteristics so that when observed at 24 HST and 31 HST the new grand rapid variety showed the highest yields.

Based on the DMRT test at the 5% level (Table 1), the interaction between Nasa LOF concentration treatment and lettuce varieties occurred at 24 DAP and 31 DAP age observations, this occurred because of the slow release nature of organic fertilizer. This is in line with the opinion of Agustina (2020) who states that organic materials have slow release properties which make it difficult for nutrients to be released, so they are slowly available to plants

Providing Nasa LOF will add nutrients that plants need. Hadisuwito (2012), states that organic fertilizer contains complete macro and micro nutrients, but in small quantities. This is in line with the opinion of Nuro (2016), which states that the application of DAPat organic fertilizer enriches the content of organic matter and macro-micro nutrients so that DAPat increases plant production. The role of the macro nutrient DAPat can be seen that the element DAPat influences the results of photosynthesis which will later have an impact on plant growth, because the more macro nutrients the plant DAPat, the photosynthesis process will reach its maximum point and plant growth will be better (Ritonga, 2020). Based on the DMRT test at 5% level (Table 3), the interaction between Nasa LOF concentration treatment and lettuce varieties occurred at 31 HST, this occurred because of the slow release nature of organic fertilizer. At the age of 31 HST Nasa LOF is completely absorbed by plants so that it is able to meet the plant's needs. This is supported by the opinion of Muhsin (2011) which states that organic fertilizer is slow release (decomposes slowly), the nutrients contained in organic fertilizer will be released slowly and continuously over a longer period of time.

Selecting the appropriate variety will also increase the number of lettuce plant leaves. Each lettuce variety has different genetics, differences in harvest time will affect the growth of the variety. The longer the vegetative period of a plant lasts, the more plant organs are formed. This is due to the influence of environmental factors and genetic factors. In line with the opinion of Sugianto (2017) which states that plant growth and development is supported by various external and internal plant factors that work together in a harmonious balance. Plant growth, such as the number of leaves, is also influenced by other factors such as the availability of nutrients, water and environmental conditions.

Based on the results of the 5% DMRT test (Table 6), it is known that the combination of K2V1 treatment (LOF Nasa concentration 6 mL/L + New Grand Rapid lettuce variety) at 31 DAP was significantly different from the K1V1, K1V2, K1V3, K2V2, K2V3, K3V1 treatments, K3V2, and K3V3 on variable wet weight per lettuce plant. It can be seen in the table that the K2V1 treatment combination produced the highest average at 31 DAP age observations. This shows that the Nasa LOF concentration of 6 mL/L is the optimal Nasa LOF concentration to increase the wet weight per plant of the new grand rapid variety of lettuce. Based on the results of the 5% BNT test (Table 4), it is known that in the single treatment of lettuce varieties V1 (lettuce variety New Grand Rapid) and V3 (lettuce variety

Kriebo LE 873) at 24 DAP were significantly different from treatment V2 regarding the observation variable of the number of plant leaves. lettuce. DAPat can be seen in the table that treatments V1, V2, and V3 produce varying averages for each observation. This shows that the genetics of each different variety cause the growth of a different number of leaves. This is in accordance with the opinion of Marliah (2012) which states that, variations that arise in plant populations grown in the same environmental conditions are variations or differences that originate from the genotypes of individual members of the population.

Plants elongate plant roots to meet water needs. This is in accordance with the opinion of Torey (2013) who states that the elongation of plant roots in an effort to find water is an indicator of plants that are tolerant of water shortages. This is confirmed by the opinion of Ai (2013) who states that root morphological characters that have the potential to indicate plant resistance to water shortages are root elongation, increase in area and depth of the root system, expansion of root distribution horizontally and vertically, increase in root volume.

Based on the results of the 5% BNT test (Table 5), it is known that in a single treatment, lettuce varieties showed a very significant influence on the root length observation variable. Based on the average of sample observations, the results show different results at each observation time. This is caused by several factors, one of which can be influenced by the genetic diversity of each plant variety. Genetic factors are a description of the potential of a plant to produce desired products, both in the form of plant results in the form of vegetative parts and plant production (Sufardi, 2020)

According to Juanda (2018), Nasa LOF is a type of liquid fertilizer which, if used at the right time and with the right concentration, can increase the process of nutrient absorption by plants because the presence of nutrients increases and also, if balanced with good maintenance, can increase plant productivity when compared with plants that do not provide Nasa LOF. This was proven in this study which showed that when observing the wet weight per lettuce plant aged 31 DAP (Table 6), there was an interaction with the lettuce variety treatment. The Nasa LOF which produces the highest average for the wet weight variable per plant is the Nasa LOF concentration of 6 mL/L. Proper Nasa LOF concentration treatment and supported by appropriate varieties can stimulate the growth of lettuce plants so that they can increase the fresh weight of lettuce plants. This is because the high production of a variety is caused by the variety being able to adapt to the environment, one of which is nutrients. This is in accordance with opinion. Sugianto (2017) who states that the potential of varieties in the field is influenced by environmental conditions at the time of research. Types of varieties that are suitable for environmental conditions are expected to grow well and provide high yields.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

There was an interaction between Nasa LOF concentration treatment and lettuce varieties on the observed variables of plant height (24 DAP and 31 DAP), number of leaves (31 DAP) and fresh weight per lettuce plant (31 DAP). A single treatment of Nasa LOF concentration had no significant effect on all observed variables of lettuce plant growth. A single treatment of lettuce varieties had an effect on the observed variables of plant height (10 DAP and 17 DAP), number of leaves (24 DAP) and root length (10 DAP, 17 DAP, 24 DAP and 31 DAP). Treatment V3 (kriebo lettuce variety) was the treatment with the highest average.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic of Effect of Nasa Liquid Organic Fertilizer (LOF) Concentration and Varieties on Growth and Production of Lettuce Plants (*Lactuca Sativa L.*) with the DFT Hydroponic System in order to improve this research and add insight to readers.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Our research team would like to thank the Dean, Head of Study Program, Ka. Lab. Agrotechnology and all parties who have helped our article to be published.

REFERENCES

- Agustina, M.D. 2020. Pengaruh Aplikasi Fungi Mikoriza Arbuskula Dan Ragam Bahan Organik Terhadap Pertumbuhan Dan Hasil Tanaman Jagung Manis (*Zea mays Saccharata*) Varietas Talenta Pada Tanah Pasca Galian C. Diploma Thesis, UIN Sunan Gunung Djati Bandung.
- Ai, N.S., Dan P. Torey. 2013. Karakter Morfologi Akar Sebagai Indikator Kekurangan Air Pada Tanaman. *Jurnal Bioslogos*. 3(1): 31-39.
- Akbar, A. 2020. Pengaruh Interval Dan Volume Penyiraman Terhadap Pertumbuhan dan Hasil Tanaman Selada Merah (*lactuca sativa var. Red romaine*). Skripsi. Fakultas Pertanian Universitas Sriwijaya.
- Hadisuwito, Sukamto. 2012. Membuat Pupuk Organik Cair. Jakarta : Agromedia
- Juanda, H., T. Nugrahini, Dan Mahdalena. 2018. Pengaruh Pemberian Pupuk Organik Cair Nasa Dan Pupuk Kompos Terhadap Pertumbuhan Tanaman Kenaf (*Hibiscus cannabinus L.*). *J.Afrifarm*. 7(1): 6-9.
- Marliah, A., T. Hidayat, dan N. Husna. 2012. Pengaruh jarak tanam dan varietas terhadap pertumbuhan kedelai (*Glycine max L.*). 16(1).
- Maulana. 2011. Pupuk Organik Cair Nasa. Diakses 17 November 2020 Dari Pcnasa.com.

- Muhsin, Ahmad. 2011. Pemanfaatan Limbah Hasil Pengolahan Pabrik Tebu Blotong Menjadi Pupuk Organik.
- Murdianto, Deden. 2016. Kajian Beberapa Varietas Dan Dosis Pupuk Petrobio TerhaDAP Pertumbuhan Dan Produksi Tanaman Sawi (*Barassica juncea* L.). Skripsi. Fakultas Pertanian. Universitas Kadiri. Kediri.
- Nuro, F., D. Priadi, Dan E.S. Mulyaningsih. 2016. Efek Pupuk Organik TerhaDAP Sifat Kimia Tanah Dan Produksi Kangkung Darat (*Ipomoea reptans* Poir.). Prosiding Seminar Nasional Hasil-Hasil PPM IPB. 2016: 29-39.
- Patti, P. S., E. Kaya Dan Ch. Silahooy. 2013. Analisis Status Nitrogen Tanah Dalam Kaitannya Dengan Serapan N Oleh Tanaman Padi Sawah Di Desa Waimital, Kecamatan Kairatu, Kabupaten Seram Bagian Barat. *J. Agrologia*. 2(1): 51-58.
- Rahmawati, A.D Dan S.Y. Tyasmoro. 2018. Respon Pertumbuhan Tiga Varietas Tanaman Selada (*Lactuca sativa* L) TerhaDAP Berbagai Jenis Nutrisi Pada Sistem Hidroponik NFT. *Jurnal Produksi Tanaman*. 6(10): 2491-2500.
- Raihan, M.N.A. 2017. Pertumbuhan Dan Perkembangan Tanaman Pakchoy (*Brassica chinensis* L.) Pada Berbagai Konsentrasi Pupuk Abmix Dan Pupuk Organik Cair (POC) Dengan Teknik Hidroponik. Skripsi. Fakultas Pertanian. Universitas Hasanuddin. Makassar.
- Ritonga, A.A., E. Efendi, Dan Safruddin. 2020. Respon Pertumbuhan Dan Produksi Tanaman Sereh (*Cymbopogon citratus*) TerhaDAP Aplikasi Npk Mutiara Dan Poc Top G2. *Agricultural Research Journal*. 16(1): 125-136.
- Sufardi. 2020. Pertumbuhan Tanaman. di akses 20 Juni 2021 dari https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341540066_PERTUMBUHAN_TANAMAN.
- Sugianto. 2017. Pengaruh Pemberian Dosis Kompos Bio N10 Dan Macam Varietas TerhaDAP Pertumbuhan Dan Produksi Tanaman Pare (*Momorcida Charantina* L.). Skripsi. Fakultas Pertanian. Universitas Kadiri. Kediri.
- Torey, P.C., N.S. Ai, P. Siahaan, Dan S.M. Mambu. 2013. Karakter Morfologi Akar Sebagai Indikator Kekurangan Air Pada Padi Lokal Superwin. *Jurnal Bios Logos*. 3(2): 57-64.
- Tuhuture, S., Dan M. Nurdin. 2020. Pemanfaatan Pupuk Organik Cair Nasa Dalam Meningkatkan Produktivitas Bawang Merah Di Daerah Wamena. *Agroteknika*. 3(2): 85-98.

- Zahima, G.A.K. Sutariati, Dan T.C. Rakian. 2019. Pertumbuhan Tanaman Selada (*Lactuca sativa* L.) Yang Dibudidayakan Secara Hidroponik Pada Berbagai Campuran Pupuk Organik Plus Cair Dan Anorganik Ab Mix. *J. Berkala Penelitian Agronomi*. 7(1): 65-73.
- Zenita, Y. M. Dan E. Widaryanto. 2019. Pengaruh Media Tanam Dan Konsentrasi Nutrisi TerhaDAP Pertumbuhan Dan Hasil Tanaman Selada Butterhead (*Lactuca sativa* Var. Capitata) Dengan Sistem Hidroponik Substrat. *Jurnal Produksi Tanaman*. 7(8): 1504-1513.